

Research

Structural and stratigraphic studies of Hazara-Kashmir Syntaxis, northwestern Himalaya, Pakistan

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Abstract: *The study area lies in the southern part of the Hazara Kashmir syntaxis, which is an antiformal structure, located in the Northwestern part of the Himalaya. It is a major tectonic feature controlling the tectonic setting at the western termination of Himalaya. The Tertiary molasse sequence lies in the core of the syntaxis, and the erosional processes of Himalaya feeds the detritus in the adjoining Foreland Basin. This molasses sequence is further divided into Chinji, Nagri, Dhok Pathan and, Soan formations, and Mirpur conglomerate.*

The molasse sequence is folded and imbricated being a part of an active fold and thrust belt in the sub-Himalaya of Pakistan. The folds are northeast-southwest trending, northwest-southeast vergent, close fold geometry and northeast or southwest plunge. The Chinji Formation lies in the core and Nagri Formation on the south-eastern limb, whereas, Malikpur-Diljaba fault truncates the northwestern limb of Tamliahn anticline.

The Malikpur-Diljaba, Tanyam and Makhlot faults are reverse faults, whereas, Jhelum fault is a left-lateral strike-slip fault, are major structures in the study area. The Jhelum fault is the youngest and an active tectonic feature in the syntaxial zone. The tectonic history reveals a north-south compressional related deformation.

Keywords: *Structure and stratigraphy, Hazara-Kashmir Syntaxis, Northwestern Himalaya, Jhelum Fault, Himalayan Foreland Basin*

1. Introduction

The Northwestern region of the Himalaya, formed as a consequence of the collision of the Indian Plate and Eurasian Plate, that uprise the Himalayan mountain system along with the closure of the Tethys Sea^{1,2}. The study area covers the southern part of Hazara Kashmir Syntaxis (HKS) Makhlot, Tanyam, Khadimabad and Malikpur areas of Azad Kashmir and situated in the sub-Himalaya of Pakistan. Tectonically, the area lies in the Northwestern portion of sub-Himalaya, more specifically in the core of HKS (Fig. 1). The core of syntaxis comprises Himalayan molasse deposits. The study area is about 70 km² and lies between longitudes 73°30'00"E to 73°40'00"E and latitudes 33°17'35"N to 33°20'20"N. The Geological Survey of Pakistan (GSP) and Azad Kashmir Mineral and Industrial Development Corporation (AKMIDC) collectively mapped the area on 1:50,000 scale and the study area falls on the toposheet No. 43G/11. The various geologists previously studied the area^{3,4,5,6,7,8}. Those studies were based on the regional stratigraphy, structure, biostratigraphy and petrography of different rock units in the area. The study area is bounded by Riasi Fault to the east, Main Boundary Thrust (MBT) to the west and the Salt Range Thrust to the south. The Jhelum Fault is running through the area, which is major left-lateral strike-slip fault. The rocks in this area are the Himalayan molasse sediments, which were deposited due to the Late Tertiary uplifting and erosion of the Himalaya⁸.

The purpose of this study is to update the geological and structural map of the area on 1:50,000 scale and to analyze the structural geometry of the area by preparing structural cross-sections. This study focuses on delineating the subsurface geology and structural elements of the area. In this paper, we set out the results of new structural studies and give an account of their tectonic significance. Additionally, the study evaluates the geometric problems related to the stratigraphy and structure of the area. The new data presented in this paper have primarily resulted from re-mapping of the region. The outcomes of this study can be helpful for a better understanding of the stratigraphy and the structure of the area with respect to HKS.

Fig. 1: Generalized geologic map of the NW Himalayan foreland fold and thrust belt, modified after⁹. The inset shows the location of the study area. MKT: Main Karakorum Thrust, MMT: Main Mantle Thrust, MBT: Main Boundary Thrust, NPDZ: Northern Potwar deformed Zone, MT: Mansehra Thrust, PT: Panjal Thrust, NT: Nathiagali Thrust, HKS: Hazara Kashmir Syntaxis, JF: Jhelum Fault, KF: Kalabagh Fault, SRT: Salt Range Thrust, TIRT: Trans Indus Range Thrust, MR: Marwat Range and KR: Khissor Range.

Fig. 2: Geological Map of Makhlot Tamliahn, Kahdimabad and Malikpur areas of Azad Kashmir, Pakistan

2. METHODOLOGY

Different traverses were made along and across the regional strike (Fig. 3). The rock units and structural data like folds and faults were plotted on the map during the fieldwork. The photographs were taken in the field to document different features of the rock units. The facing criteria like rip ups and cross-bedding were used to determine the top and bottom of the stratigraphic units. The route and traverse map, geological map, structural map and structural cross-sections were prepared with the acquired structural data from the field. The structural cross-section was constructed by using kink method. At the same time, the thickness of the geological formations was adopted from surface measurement data of previous literature in the surroundings of the study area. This method requires dip measurement data to define a zone where the dip is constant, whereas the boundaries of the dip zones are the lines that bisect angles between adjacent dips.

Fig. 3: Route and Traverse Map of Makhlot Tamliahn, Kahdimabad and Malikpur areas of Azad Kashmir, Pakistan

3. GEOLOGY OF THE AREA

The study area is the part of the Himalayan Foreland Basin consisting of Siwalik Group of rocks having Miocene to Pliocene molasse sequence and Pleistocene Mirpur Conglomerates (Fig. 2). The Siwalik Group clastic sediments are assumed to have been eroded from the metamorphic rocks of the Himalayan Orogeny^{10, 11}. These thick units of clastic sediments are separated by a major unconformity from the Eocene marine facies^{12,13}. Based on palaeontological data, the Siwalik Group has been classified into Lower, Middle and Upper Siwaliks¹⁴. These three distinct types of Siwalik subunits that occur in the study area are represented mainly by mudstone facies, significantly sandstone facies and sandstone plus conglomerate facies following stratigraphic sequence upward (Fig. 4). The exposed rock sequence includes the Chinji Formation, Nagri Formation, Dhok Pathan Formation, Soan Formation, and Mirpur Conglomerates. The lithological description of these rocks is described.

Fig. 4: Generalized stratigraphic terminology of the Siwalik Group (modified after¹⁵). (a) Sedimentary facies of Siwaliks (b) (c) Log, redrawn from Willis (1993) showing mean grain-size averaged for every meter interval. Letters A, B and C indicate intervals studied in detail¹⁶.

3.1 Chinji Formation

The Chinji Formation which is exposed in Tamliah and Harno Villages consists of mudstone, siltstone and sandstone. Mudstones are about 60% to 70% and sandstone is 30% to 40%. The clays are brick red, maroon, grey, purple, red and ash grey, whereas, the sandstone is ash grey to grey (Fig. 5a). The sandstone is fine- to medium-grained, medium to thickly bedded, occasionally gritty, cross-bedded and soft. The sandstone is softer, easily erodible and also shows patchy weathering at certain places. Following the sandstone, the much thicker claystone beds do appear, which are poorly sorted and have a light grey, brown and orange-red colour. The sandstone and clay beds have cyclic bedding. The sandstones of the Chinji Formation are generally moderately sorted with sub-angular to sub-rounded grains. The essential minerals of sandstone are quartz and feldspar

whereas the accessory minerals are biotite, chlorite, garnet and tourmaline. The Chinji Formation is easily erodible due to high clay content and shows low relief. This unit is of Middle to Late Miocene age¹⁷.

3.2 Nagri Formation

In the study area, the Nagri Formation is exposed in Khoi Las, Makhlot and Balyam areas. The Nagri Formation consists of alternating sandstone and mudstone. The sandstone is greenish grey cross-bedded and massive (Fig. 5b) and weathered condition dark grey to brownish-grey. The sandstone is medium- to coarse-grained, hard and compact. The sandstone and clay ratio in the Nagri formation is about 3:2.

Fig. 5: (a) Sandstone (A) and variegated clays (B) of Chinji Formation near Tamliahan. (b) Cross bedding in Nagri Formation near Makhlot (c) Cyclic bedding of sandstone (A) and clay (B) of Dhok Pathan Formation near Sarahna Gora

The sandstone is generally composed of quartz, feldspar and biotite with accessory minerals epidote, tourmaline and muscovite. The biotite is abundant in the sandstone of Nagri Formation. The sandstone is characterized by salt and pepper texture. The clay of Nagri Formation is sandy or silty, brown to reddish grey. The intraformational pseudo-conglomerates composed of mud pellets, pebbles of volcanic rocks, and balls of sandstone and clay in the sandy matrix are common in the lower and upper part of the formation. These conglomerates occur as thin beds, lenses, or strings. The volcanic clasts are only present in the upper part of the Nagri Formation. The age of the Nagri Formation is Late Miocene¹⁷.

3.3 Dhok Pathan Formation

In the study area, the Dhok Pathan Formation is exposed in Taliam, Gora and Thala areas. This formation consists of sandstone, clays and hard, thick and compact conglomeratic layers. The sandstone is light grey and reddish-brown and relatively soft with respect to the Nagri Formation.

The sandstone is composed of quartz, feldspar, muscovite, brown garnet, pink garnet, epidote, minor tourmaline and biotite. The Dhok Pathan Formation is characterized by cyclic bedding of shale and sandstone (Fig. 5c). The shale of this formation is orange, brown, dull red or reddish-brown, yellowish-grey, chocolate-colored, calcareous and sandy. The conglomerate layers contain clasts of Punjal volcanic, metamorphic and older sedimentary rocks. The clasts range from 2 mm to 5 cm in diameter. The false bedding and ribbed topography are the characteristic features of Dhok Pathan Formation. Both the lower contact of Dhok Pathan Formation with the Nagri Formation and upper contact with Soan Formation is gradational. The Dhok Pathan Formation can be distinguished from Nagri formation on the basis of ribbed topography, lenticular bedding and pink garnets. The age of the Dhok Pathan formation is Late Miocene¹⁷.

3.4 Soan Formation

The Soan Formation is exposed in Behgam, Chakbandand and Banrajgan areas. The Soan Formation consists of polymict conglomerates, layers of sandstone, siltstone and clays (Fig. 6a). The lower part of Soan Formation is composed of sandstone and clay with subordinate conglomerate beds. The sandstone is fragile, coarse-grained and less compacted. The sandstone is composed of quartz, biotite, hornblende and garnet. The bentonite clay is found at the base of Soan Formation (Fig. 6b).

The upper part of Soan Formation is mainly exposed in Banrajgan area. It consists of thick, hard and massive conglomerates with minor clays. The conglomerates contain pebbles and boulders of quartzite, limestone, cherty dolomite and granite gneisses. The clays are brown, yellowish and grey. The upper contact of the Soan Formation with Mirpur Formation is angular unconformable. The age of Soan Formation is Pliocene¹⁷.

Fig. 6: (a) The photograph shows conglomeratic bed (A) and sandy beds (B) of Soan Formation near Ban-Rajgan. (b) The photograph showing the bentonite clay in the basal part of Soan Formation at Behgam

3.5 Mirpur Formation

In the study area, the Mirpur Formation is exposed in Kandor and Khari areas. The Mirpur Formation consists of conglomerate. The clasts are well rounded and loosely packed within the clayey and silty matrix. The clasts of quartz, feldspar, limestone, sandstone, Punjal volcanic and granite are present in Mirpur Formation. The conglomerates of Mirpur Formation have a clayey matrix. An angular unconformity is present between Mirpur Formation and Soan Formation. The age of the Formation is Pleistocene¹⁷.

4. STRUCTURE OF THE AREA

The study area, which lies to the south of Hazara Kashmir Syntaxis is highly deformed into folds and faults due to the Himalayan Orogeny. The Main Boundary Thrust bound the study area to the west and Salt Range Thrust to the south, whereas Riasi Fault is to the east. The detailed structure map of the area having major folds and faults were prepared (Fig. 2). The detail description of these structures is as follows:

Fig. 7: (a) Folding of Chinji Formation in the core of Tamliahn anticline (b) The Photograph showing Malikpur-Diljaba fault near Tamliahn. The Chinji Formation (A) is thrust over Dhok Pathan Formation (B). (c) The Photograph showing Makhlot Fault near Tany. The Chinji Formation (B) is thrust over the Nagri Formation (A). (d) The Photograph showing Tanyam Fault near Sarahna Gora. The Chinji Formation is thrust over the Nagri Formation (B), the (C) marks the deformation zone along fault.

4.1 Folds

4.1.1 Tamliahn Anticline

The Tamliahn anticline was formed by the folding of Chinji and Nagri formations (Fig. 6). The Chinji Formation is at the core whereas the Nagri Formation lies on the limbs. The northwestern limb is relatively steeper than the south-eastern limb (Fig. 7a). The strike of the northwestern limb varies from N33°E to N45°E, whereas the strike of the south-eastern limb varies from N50°E to N60°E. The dip of the northwestern limb varies from 74°NW to 83°NW whereas the dip of the south-eastern limb varies from 48°SE to 65°SE. The northwest limb of the anticline is cut by the Malikpur-Diljaba fault whereas the south-eastern limb is cut by the Makhlot fault (Fig. 8). The attitude of the axial plane varies from N43°E/81°SE to N53°E/67°SE). The trend and plunge of the fold axis vary from 5°/226° to 23°/222°. The inter-limb angle varies from 41° to 52°. On the basis of interlimb angle the fold is classified as close fold. Tamliahn anticline is an asymmetric northwest vergent fold.

Fig. 8: Structural cross-section of the Tamliahn anticline

4.2 Faults

The study area is the part of Himalayan fold-and-thrust belt. The faults present in the area are Jhelum Fault, Malikpur-Diljaba Fault, Makhlot Fault and Tanyam Fault. These are the splay faults of the Jhelum strike slip fault. These faults are described as below:

4.2.1 Jhelum Fault

The Jhelum fault is a major fault running through study area in northwest-southeast direction⁴. This fault passes through the Thalan and Kamalpur area on the left bank of the Jhelum River. The major portion of the fault is concealed along the Jhelum River (Fig. 2). The Jhelum fault is a left lateral strike slip fault. The attitude of the fault plane is N40°E/55°NW. The shearing, crushing, fault breccia and gouge are present along the fault zone. The drag folds are common along this fault.

4.2.2 Malikpura-Diljaba Fault

The Malikpur-Diljaba fault is a major reverse fault present in the area having northeast southwest trending. The Chinji Formation is thrust over the Dhok Pathan Formation. The Chinji Formation is in the hanging wall, whereas the Dhok Pathan Formation in the footwall (Fig. 7b). The attitude of the fault plane is N43°E/80°SE. The shearing, crushing and gouge are present along the fault.

4.2.3 Makhlot Fault

The Makhlot fault is a reverse fault having a northeast-southwest trending fault (Fig. 8). The fault is present between Chinji and Nagri formations. The Chinji Formation is a thrust over Nagri Formation. The Chinji Formation is exposed on the hanging wall while the Nagri Formation is on the footwall (Fig. 7c). The attitude of fault plane is N50°E/75°SE. The deformation in the form of shearing and crushing of strata is present in the footwall as well as in the hanging wall. The gouge and breccia are present along the fault plane.

4.2.4 Tanyam Fault

The Tanyam Fault is a reverse fault between Nagri and Chinji formations. The Chinji Formation is a thrust over the Nagri Formation. The hanging wall comprises Chinji Formation whereas the footwall contains Nagri Formation. The fault is extending northeast-southwest. The attitude of the fault plane is N50°E/58°SE. The shearing and crushing are present along the fault plane. The Nagri Formation is highly deformed along the fault plane (Fig. 7d). The reverse nature of the faulting is relatively confined to higher topography on the northeastern part of the area where the strike-slip nature of the Jhelum fault affects its topography and result in high angle reverse faulting (Fig. 2).

5. DISCUSSION

The study area is a part of Sub-Himalaya of Pakistan, which lies in the southern part of HKS. The HKS is an antiformal structure formed due to the change in thrust direction from northeast to northwest. The rock units exposed in the study area are sedimentary in nature. The age of rock units is from Middle Miocene to Pleistocene including the Chinji, Nagri, Dhok Pathan and Soan formations. The area is severely deformed, sheared and fractured due to onward collision between Indian and Eurasian plates. The fold present in the area is Tamlianh anticline. This fold is a northeast-southwest trending, northwest verging and southwest plunging anticline. The Tamliahn anticline is formed by the folding of the Chinji and Nagri formations. The Chinji Formation is at

the core of the anticline, whereas, the Nagri Formation is on the limbs. The structural analysis derived from field measurements and structural cross section suggests that these faults are responsible for propagating the folds in the study area. The major faults of the area are the Jhelum fault, Malikpur-Diljaba fault, Makhlot fault and Tanyam fault. The Malikpur-Diljaba, Makhlot and Tanyam faults are reverse faults. These faults were generated from early to Late Miocene as derived from stratigraphic sedimentary succession of the study area.

Fig. 9: Structural Cross sections of the Tanyam fault and Makhlot fault

The Malikpur-Diljaba fault is marked between the Chinji and the Dhok Pathan formations. The Chinji Formation is thrust over the Dhok Pathan Formation. The attitude of the fault plane is N43°E/80°SE. The Makhlot fault is a reverse fault. The fault is present between Chinji and Nagri formations. The Chinji Formation is thrust over Nagri Formation. The attitude of fault plane is N50°E/75°SE. The Tanyam Fault is a reverse fault and is present between Nagri and Chinji formations. The Chinji Formation is thrust over the Nagri Formation. The fault is extending northeast-southwest. The attitude of the fault plane is N50°E/58°SE. The strike slip nature of the Jhelum fault affects the topography of these faults and result in high angle reverse faulting on the northeastern part of the area. The detailed structural analysis indicates that the folding and faulting of the southern part of HKS is mainly controlled by thrust tectonics and strike-slip movements of Jhelum fault. The primary sedimentary structures like rip up and cross-bedding are present in the study area. The facing of the formations is marked on the basis of these sedimentary structures.

5 CONCLUSION

The folds and faults are the result of Himalayan orogeny in the project area. These are formed by northeast-southwest Himalayan compression. The Chinji, Nagri, Dhok Pathan and Soan formations are the molasse deposits that represent the part of cover sequence of the Indian Plate. The molasse deposits are formed due to the uplift, erosion and deposition in the Foreland Basin. The major fold of the area is Tamlianh anticline having a northeast-southwest trend. The fold is of close geometry, southwest plunging and northwest vergent. The major faults encountered were the Malikpur-Diljaba, Makhlot, Tanyam of reverse nature while Jhelum fault is a strike slip fault. The Jhelum fault truncates the major structures. In contrast, its strike-slip nature affects the topography of these structure and generates the high angle reverse faulting in the northeastern part of the area.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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